

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Turgunova Muxlisaxon Abdulxay qizi

FURQAT LIRIKASI VA UNING G'AZALLARIDAGI BOSH MAVZU

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

IF(Impact Factor) 7.2 / 2023

ISSN: 3030-3168

2024/AVGUST

